

The Gamification Quest

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Keywords

Behavioral Design, Collaborative Problem-solving, Competence Development, Educational Ethics, Gamification, Octalysis Framework, Psychology, Reflective Learning

Figure 1. Participants playing *The Gamification Quest* during a workshop at Leuphana University. © Game Didaktiks Project, Leuphana University.

Introduction

The Gamification Quest (see Figure 1) is an educational board game that introduces the core principles of gamification through the Octalysis Framework, a model that describes human motivation through eight core psychological drives that shape engagement and behavior in gamified systems (Chou, 2014). The Gamification Quest was developed in September 2025 by Lucian Alikhani, Johannes Katsarov, and Maya Kim within the Game Didaktiks Project at

Leuphana University, in the hope of helping university educators explore how motivational design can enhance teaching and learning.

Its movement system echoes classic race games such as Mensch ärgere dich nicht or Snakes and Ladders, where players advance toward a goal but risk being sent back if they fail a challenge or collide with another player. The path is color-coded according to the eight Core Drives of Octalysis, and progress depends on players solving scenario-based tasks that require identifying, matching, and justifying game mechanics for each drive.

Situated within the field of serious games, The Gamification Quest bridges theory and practice by turning abstract ideas about motivation and behavior design into a tangible, collaborative learning experience.

Facts

Release date:	10.11.2025
Developer:	Lucian Alikhani, Johannes Katsarov, Maya Kim, within the Game Didaktiks Project at Leuphana University
Game type:	Analog
Number of players:	2–4
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	20–40 minutes
Languages:	English, German
Environment:	The board game and the cards need to be printed.
Material:	All the material can be downloaded for free and printed. https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17570890
Price:	Free

Resonance & Criticism

As The Gamification Quest is a newly developed prototype, it has been tested only twice to date in two workshops by the Game Didaktiks Project at Leuphana University. Early feedback from educators and participants was positive, emphasizing the game's ability to stimulate meaningful reflection on motivational design and learning mechanisms. However, some participants in the first workshop noted that the pace of play could be improved and that additional interactive elements might enhance engagement. These criticisms were taken into consideration, and adjustments were made accordingly for the second workshop, which received only positive feedback, although it should be noted that the sample size was very limited. As a recent prototype, the game has not yet been widely implemented or received formal ratings or awards.

Game Principle & Process

The game is played with 2-4 participants, called Candidates within the game lore. Players journey across the board toward the Castle of Mastery. The game is turn-based and uses three decks: the Main Deck (with Spark and Risk cards), the Challenge Deck, and the Sabotage Deck. Each player also receives a small reference card summarizing the eight Core Drives.

On their turn, a player draws from the Main Deck. Spark cards describe a gamification mechanism, and the player must match it to one or more Core Drives. A correct answer allows the player to advance along the matching color path to the corresponding tile. An incorrect answer keeps the player in place. Risk cards describe common pitfalls in gamification design; a correct response lets the player remain on the space, while an incorrect response obligates the player to step back to the previous mushroom tile.

Mushroom tiles act as checkpoints. Landing on a mushroom tile triggers a Challenge card that presents a classroom scenario in which the player must choose the most suitable gamification mechanism. If the answer is correct, the player is awarded a Sabotage card. Sabotage cards allow the player to hinder another player's progress or improve their own position, depending on the effect written on the Sabotage card, and may be used immediately.

If two players land on the same space, the one who was already there is sent back to the previous mushroom and must answer a Challenge card; failure sends them back to the start. Each turn is limited to two minutes, ensuring the pace remains dynamic and that all participants stay engaged. The game concludes when a player reaches the castle and successfully answers a final Challenge card, demonstrating mastery of the journey.

The authors of the game drew upon several sources in motivational psychology and gamification to inform the cards' content (e.g., Ryan & Deci, 2000; Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi, 2018; Liberty, 2024; Chou, 2014; Hamari et al., 2014; Sailer et al., 2017).

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

This game is designed to foster a conceptual and practical understanding of motivational design in higher education. Its central learning objective is to help educators recognize, analyze, and apply the principles of the Octalysis Framework to their own teaching contexts. Through play, participants explore how specific gamification mechanisms, such as leaderboards, follower systems, or time-bound rewards, can influence learner motivation and engagement.

The game promotes three interrelated competencies:

1. Analytical competence: Identifying and differentiating the eight Core Drives through Spark cards;
2. Design competence: Selecting and justifying appropriate mechanics for specific educational goals through Challenge cards;

3. Reflective competence: Evaluating the ethical and pedagogical implications of motivational design choices through Risk cards.

The Spark cards encourage pattern recognition between theoretical drives and concrete mechanics. Challenge cards simulate authentic classroom dilemmas that demand applied reasoning and justification. Sabotage cards introduce a meta-layer of strategic and emotional engagement, prompting reflection on how competitive and cooperative dynamics affect motivation, mirroring real-world challenges in teaching (for example, leaderboards might, in some contexts, reduce student motivation by rewarding only the top-performing students and ignoring others).

The game is designed to serve as a stand-alone educational tool. Therefore, the role of facilitators is limited to moderating the game. This role does not require any prior knowledge. However, familiarity with the basics of gamification and motivation theory can be helpful at times. Preparation time is minimal: after a brief (10-minute) introduction to the game based on the rule book, the facilitator can start the session.

Educationally, The Gamification Quest falls under teacher training, instructional design, educational psychology, and higher education pedagogy. It can be used as a stand-alone workshop, a seminar exercise, or a reflective intervention in professional development programs.

Effectiveness

As this game is a newly developed prototype, no empirical studies have yet been conducted. However, initial players found it engaging and valued the opportunity to reflect on the gamification mechanisms as they explored the motivational foundations behind each. Future research could empirically evaluate the game's effectiveness in transferring knowledge and in fostering engagement.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

The game does not address any sensitive topics such as violence, discrimination, or mental health issues. However, minor concerns may arise from the competitive elements introduced by Sabotage cards, which could disadvantage less confident participants if not carefully moderated. The game relies on abstract examples and simplified scenarios, which may limit cultural inclusivity. Ethical facilitation is recommended to ensure balanced participation and sensitivity to differing teaching contexts.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl

Sources

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